

Semantic Annotation for the Ancient World

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Book of Abstracts

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Contents

Acknowledgements	3
Foreword	4
Keynote Speakers	5
Low-Resource Languages and Epistemic Justice, Annie K. Lamar	5
Oh LAWD, oh LAWD, oh LAWD: Reflections on Linked Ancient World Data projects, Terhi Nurmikko-Fuller	5
1 Contributed Abstracts	6
1.1 Session 1: Corpus Linguistics	6
Semantic annotation of Latin documents using Computer-Assisted Semantic Text Modelling (CASTEMO) and the InkVisitor application	6
An Alternative Model of LLM-Assisted Annotation: Exploring NL2Code for Frame-Semantic Annotation of Early Arabic Poetry	6
Annotating Semantic Features in a Diachronic Corpus of Latin: Strategies for a Semi-Automatic Approach	9
Automatic detection of formulaic expressions in Ancient Greek scientific (technical) texts	12
1.2 Session 2: Fine-tuning and Vectorization	13
A Comparative Study of Static and Dynamic Vector Representations for Semantic Search in a Corpus of Classical Latin Texts	13
Automatically enriching the GLAUx corpus with semantic role annotation	15
Metadata conditioning for premodern Greek language models: Text annotation to preserve authorial style and meter in ancient text reconstruction	17
1.3 Session 3: Annotation Workflows	20
Modular Annotation Framework for Ancient Greek Pedagogy	20
Semi-Automated Semantic Annotation of Buddhist Murals: Integrating Foundation Models into a Digital Humanities Workflow	23
1.4 Session 4: Annotating Material Culture	26
Project RelNet: annotating temples, rituals and networks in Late Babylonia	26
A Bridge between Text and Image: Multimodal AI and Ancient Greek Cultural Objects .	27
Evidence-Graded Semantic Annotation and Spatial Graph-RAG for Water Infrastructure in the Nile Valley (500 BCE–300 CE)	30
1.5 Session 5: Human-in-the-loop Annotation	33
Rethinking Genre Classification and the Digitally-Annotated Great Unread: The Case of Talmudic Stories	33
Coding Narrative Dynamics in Plutarch’s Metaphors	34
Coding the Uncodable? Manual Semantic Annotation of Cognition Metaphors in Plutarch Between Interpretive Labor and Hybrid AI Workflows	36
Keyword Index	40
Author Index	41

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Foreword

The Semantic Annotation for the Ancient World conference, begun in 2025, focuses on methods, standards, and tools for the semantic annotation of historical, literary, and cultural heritage materials. We welcome contributions relating to:

- Ontology-based models and frameworks for semantic annotation
- Methods for multilingual and cross-lingual semantic annotation of historical and literary corpora
- Automatic, semi-automatic, and assisted annotation pipelines, including annotation interfaces and workflow design
- Semantic enrichment of texts and images through entity recognition, linking to controlled vocabularies, and ontology alignment
- Use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative AI for annotation, enrichment, disambiguation, and knowledge extraction
- Human–AI collaborative annotation strategies, including expert validation, iterative refinement, and quality control
- Integration of annotated corpora with Knowledge Graphs and Linked Open Data ecosystems
- Computational philology approaches that rely on or produce semantically enriched corpora
- Digital Classics and Cultural Heritage infrastructures supporting annotation, curation, and data interoperability
- Ethical and epistemological considerations in AI-supported semantic annotation, including transparency, provenance, and interpretability

Keynote Speakers

Keynote 1: Low-Resource Languages and Epistemic Justice

Speaker: Assistant Prof. Annie K. Lamar, UC Santa Barbara, USA

Abstract: The rapid expansion of large language models and data-intensive AI is widening the gap in technological equity. Most cutting-edge LLMs and the annotated data used to train them systematically advantage high-resource languages. This trend threatens to further marginalize historical, scarce, and endangered linguistic datasets. The aggressive push toward algorithmic scale compounds this problem and enables extractive practices—what I call "digital prospecting"—that compromise community data sovereignty in favor of corporate model training.

This talk applies the framework of epistemic justice to AI development: specifically, its commitments to the fair distribution of epistemic resources and the recognition of non-dominant knowledge systems. Central to this intervention is the positioning of Classics as a 'model science'. By treating the small data environments of ancient Mediterranean languages as an opportunity for innovation rather than a limitation, we can develop "humanist-in-the-loop" methodologies that prioritize human expertise and allot interpretive authority to the communities whose linguistic heritage is at stake. This talk demonstrates how the rigorous constraints of computational classics provide a roadmap for building AI futures that are ethical, transparent, and linguistically diverse.

Biography: Annie K. Lamar is Assistant Professor of Computational Classics and Director of the Low-Resource Language (LOREL) Lab at the University of California, Santa Barbara. Her research sits at the intersection of classical philology, natural language processing, and computational humanities, with a sustained focus on multilingual vector stability. She has published on machine translation, geospatial computation, and the linguistic marginalization of underrepresented communities in AI infrastructures. Her public writing has appeared in Newsweek, Tech Policy Press, and Inside Higher Ed. She holds an MA in Education Data Science and a PhD in Classics from Stanford University.

Keynote 2: Oh LAWD, oh LAWD, oh LAWD: Reflections on Linked Ancient World Data projects

Speaker: Associate Prof. Terhi Nurmikko-Fuller, RMIT University, Australia

Abstract: The Linked Ancient World Data Initiative ran its first iterations in 2012 and 2013. This event was a pivotal moment, creating communities, collaborations, and publications. This talk will discuss example projects within this space, highlight the value of applying semantic technologies to ancient world data, and celebrate the communities which have engaged and pioneered in this niche specialism. It pulls on heuristics of past projects, flags the dangers of presentism, and asks whether digital technologies that have been built from the omniscient perspectives of complete, clean, and modern data can truly be applied to the incomplete, ambiguous, and heterogenous datasets that map the ancient world in ways that are accurate, true, or even simply unproblematic.

Biography: Dr Terhi Nurmikko-Fuller is an Associate Professor, Information Interaction at the School of Computing Technologies at RMIT University in Melbourne, Australia. Her interdisciplinary research examines different methods for data linking and integration, and how digital technologies support and diversify research. She is the author of "Linked Data for Digital Humanities" (2023, Routledge), and has publications that cover a range of topics from the use, development, and critical evaluation of Linked Data to gamification and informal online environments in education. She has also created 3D digital models for the British Museum (cuneiform tablets), the National Museum of Australia (carved boab nuts), and UNESCO (Fels Cave in Vanuatu). Terhi is an Honorary Associate Professor at POLIS, the Centre for Social Policy and Research at the Australian National University; a member of the Territory Records Advisory Council, Policy and Cabinet Division, of the Chief Minister Australian Capital Territory Government; and a co-chair of the Australian Government Linked Data Working Group.

1 Contributed Abstracts

1.1 Session 1: Corpus Linguistics

Semantic annotation of Latin documents using Computer-Assisted Semantic Text Modelling (CASTEMO) and the InkVisitor application

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This paper presents the principles and workflow of Computer-Assisted Semantic Text Modelling (CASTEMO) and the InkVisitor application which embodies this workflow. CASTEMO is based on two principles: standard ontology building through a lexico-semantic network of Actions (verbs and verbal expressions) and Concepts (other parts of speech), and modelling clauses as statements, which together form a powerful and well-queryable knowledge graph. Statements follow a quadruple structure, reflecting the ubiquity of clauses containing both direct and indirect objects, and link entity/ies in a “subject” slot to those in the “actant 1” and “actant 2” slots (i.e. objects) via an entity filling the “action” slot. These slots can be modified to reflect semantic nuance: for instance, the “action” slot has “mood” (e.g. “indication”, “question”, “allegation” etc.) and “mood variant” (“realis”, “irrealis”) options for capturing the semantic modality. Other varieties of quadruple – Relations (basic semantic and ontological relationships), References (linking information to a source), and Properties (any other sort of characterization) – allow entities to be extensively characterized. The knowledge graph is held together semantically through a flexible, user-defined network linked by semantic Relations (e.g. synonymy, hypernymy, holonymy, but also less common, yet analytically extremely useful relations such as those which place verbs into a nominal hypernym path). Meanwhile, epistemic levels (“textual”, “interpretive”, “inferential”) clarify the relationship of data statements or any element within them to the source text, delineating textual modelling from analytical additions, thereby underlining the power of the approach to properly trace levels of annotation.

The CASTEMO approach to semantic annotation makes it possible to closely translate sources in their original languages into flexible models ready for data analysis. Our use case is medieval inquisition records, but the approach and InkVisitor are both developed as generalist. They are thus open to encompassing all kinds of literary and documentary sources in historical languages. The presentation introduces InkVisitor and provides a user-experience-oriented comparison with three alternative interfaces – CATMA, Nodegoat, and ATAG – according to sixteen criteria ranging from document management, multiuser collaboration, and XML import/export through the speed and convenience of entity creation and relationship modelling during annotation to querying and visualisation of the resulting data.

Keywords: semantic annotation, ontology building, clause modeling, quadruple, historical research

An Alternative Model of LLM-Assisted Annotation: Exploring NL2Code for Frame-Semantic Annotation of Early Arabic Poetry

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Medieval Arabo-Muslim philologists considered Early Arabic Poetry (EAP), the oral poetry of Late Antiquity Arabians, as a repository of traditional knowledge recorded and transmitted by generations of folk poets of Northern and Central Arabia [16, pp. 40][13, pp. 47].

In this paper, we explore a semi-automatic, LLM-assisted annotation method to be applied to EAP verses, while building the *Ethno-Lexicographic Early Arabic Poetry Network* database (ethnoEAP-Net) – a repository that aims at representing the traditional folk knowledge of Late Antiquity Arabians using the Frame Semantics-based *FrameNet* model augmented with Cognitive Linguistic notions of profiling [18, pp. 110] and conceptual metaphors, metonymies, and blends [17, pp. 475, 477].

Using LLMs for annotation automation is a growing trend in NLP [8, pp. 2]. It has also been applied to *FrameNet*-related annotation tasks [4][3][2], especially employing LOME (*Linguistically-Oriented Meaning Representation*), a LLM-based frame-semantic parser [20]. The scope of the LLM employment in these tasks has been limited to expanding the coverage of *FrameNet* annotation in languages with existing *FrameNet* databases. Since there is no functioning *FrameNet* repository for Arabic, we propose a new model of LLM-assisted annotation procedure.

Unlike existing human-in-the-loop approaches, our model does not rely on task-level division of labor between humans and LLMs. Its core concept is to perform a NL2Code (*Natural-Language-to-Code*) task [19, pp. 375][12, pp. 140:4], i.e., a task in which a LLM generates executable code from a plain-language description. In our pilot study, we generated Python scripts limited in their functionality to a single task or a set of simple tasks facilitating the later manual annotation. We used the Claude Opus 4.6 model and SCoT (Structured Chain-of-Thought), a prompt engineering technique that structures intermediate reasoning steps to improve code generation quality [11]. The generated codes were used for automatic data generation with no human input. Before its implementation, it was evaluated in terms of reliability and validity. Our annotation model is represented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1

Our annotation task was a full-text or running-text annotation procedure [15, pp. 19]. It involved adding semantic and conceptual information to the dependency-treebank annotated texts (cf. [6]) derived from the *Camel Tree Bank* (CamelTB), a dependency treebank of Modern Standard and CA [7]. It was performed using INCEPTION, a web-based annotation tool [10][5], in two stages: LLM-assisted automatic pre-annotation and manual validation and complementary annotation.

The automatic pre-annotation required producing lexical data: (1) lemmatizing source texts using the CAMEL-Lab Analyzer [14] and the CAMELMORPH MSA morphological database [9], and (2) manually curating the lemmatization data (including English glosses) to create lexical data in the form of entries for identified lemmas.

The automatic pre-annotation involved annotating the texts for (1) employed lexical units and (2) frame proposals. Lexical unit annotation was generated based on the lexical data that were projected onto the source texts by a script. The texts had been uploaded to INCEPTION with defined customized layers and extracted as a JSON file. In this file, the script created a Lexical Unit object for each identified lemma. The frame proposal annotation was performed using a script that parsed the Lexical Unit objects with

any possibly corresponding English frame, using the *FrameNet* dataset [1] and English glosses recorded within the lexical data.

The subsequent manual validation and complementary annotation task was performed by a human annotator, and it included verifying and adjusting automatically generated frame proposals and annotating the text for additional information, such as the Frame Element instantiation.

In our pilot study, we tested our model on a sample of the CamelTB texts consisting of 86 words drawn from 9 EAP verses. The initial results indicate the reported English *FrameNet*'s coverage problem [4, pp. 2]. Consequently, many English glosses recorded within Arabic lexical data could not be parsed with any English frame. The problem appears to predominantly involve nominal lexical units. This aligns with the prevailing *FrameNet* annotation targeting scheme, favoring verbs and verbal frames [15, pp. 8].

The main contribution of our paper is a novel LLM-assisted annotation model in which LLMs serve not as direct annotators but as code generators, producing reusable Python tools that automate preparatory data-processing steps while keeping semantic judgments under full human control. This model is especially suited to low-resource languages lacking existing *FrameNet* repositories.

Keywords: frame semantics, NL2Code, early Arabic poetry, classical Arabic

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Annotating Semantic Features in a Diachronic Corpus of Latin: Strategies for a Semi-Automatic Approach

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Linguistic Background

Automatic annotation for Latin has made significant progress recently, thanks to new NLP tools and resources such as the LiLa knowledge base [18]. However, lexical semantic annotation remains underdeveloped. Existing datasets mostly rely on limited manually annotated samples, some mapping corpus occurrences to dictionary senses [17] and others [8] mapping Latin words to WordNet synsets (sets of synonymous words representing a single concept), enabling cross-linguistic alignment and providing important data for evaluating computational models of meaning.

Metaphor is widely recognised as centrally important to semantic innovation [13][23], and shifts along the concrete–abstract continuum are key patterns of semantic change [1][11]. In Latin, metaphorical reanalysis and abstraction are particularly documented in technical domains (e.g., [14][7]) but have not been studied at scale. While limited in corpus coverage, the Lexicon Translativum Latinum [10][3] documents conceptual metaphors in Latin texts, providing a framework to study how words shift across domains and acquire figurative meanings.

In this paper we analyse under-studied dimensions in Latin annotation: lexical senses, metaphorical extensions, and concreteness/abstractness, to enable large-scale diachronic analyses.

Computational background

The emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs), which can generate, translate, and interpret Latin with surprising fluency [5][21], opens new possibilities for semantic annotation while raising crucial questions. LLMs often lack temporal grounding [19] and rely on undated training data, which challenges their application to historical texts. Their ability to identify concrete/abstract senses, or track sense trajectories on diachronic Latin has been evaluated only in limited contexts [9][16]. Other semantic

capabilities (e.g., discriminating literal from metaphorical meaning) have been studied primarily in modern languages [24][20], with only preliminary experiments on Latin, particularly regarding diachronic change [15][6]. It remains unclear which annotation strategies most effectively support LLM-assisted semantic annotation in Latin. One approach consists in mapping words to WordNet synsets, which provide a structured, cross-linguistically aligned representation of meaning, but whose granularity has been discussed [4][2][12]. Another strategy consists in using English dictionary glosses, which are intuitive and human-readable, yet risk oversimplifying sense distinctions and introducing translation bias. Additionally, graded sense-relatedness schemes [22] capture degrees of semantic similarity between senses, offering fine-grained information for model guidance, but require more complex annotation protocols and calibration. Investigating how these strategies interact with LLM outputs is essential for developing semi-automatic workflows capable of reliably analyse semantics in Latin corpora.

Research Questions

In this study, we examine how different annotation strategies influence the ability of LLM-assisted workflows to capture Latin lexical semantics. We mainly focus on three dimensions of semantic annotation: sense distinctions, which allow us to track polysemy and lexical innovation; metaphorical usage, which captures figurative extensions central to Latin literature and technical discourse; and concreteness/abstractness distinctions, which enable systematic studies of cognitive and cultural patterns in lexical evolution. We investigate how the effectiveness of LLM-assisted semantic annotation varies across linguistic, semantic, and contextual factors. We examine part-of-speech (verbs, nouns, adjectives) and lexical frequency to determine whether frequent or morphologically simple items are annotated more reliably than rare or complex forms. We assess the impact of a word’s position along the concrete–abstract continuum, asking whether shifts toward abstraction are more challenging than changes within the same level of concreteness/abstractness. We examine whether LLM-assisted annotation performs differently depending on figurative language type, comparing literal, metaphorical, and metonymic usages, and distinguishing between conceptual and poetic metaphorical expressions. Sense structure is also considered, evaluating whether high polysemy or fine-grained sense inventories reduce annotation reliability. We compare annotation formats, contrasting binary schemes (e.g., English glosses or WordNet synsets) with graded representations of semantic relatedness. Finally, we explore the contribution of contextual metadata (text type, genre, register, historical period) to determine whether explicit information about genre or era improves model performance in capturing semantic distinctions.

Methodology

We employ three LLMs with the strongest performance on Latin semantic tasks [9]: GPT-5, Qwen3-235B-A22B-Thinking-2507, and DeepSeek-R1-0328. We test a range of prompting strategies to evaluate how different forms of guidance affect annotation quality: (i) fully open prompts asking the model to annotate a word in context; (ii) prompts providing candidate WordNet synsets or English glosses; and (iii) prompts supplying English meanings either as bare labels or with brief explanatory definitions to assess the effect of explicit disambiguation. We also explore prompts that emphasize a single semantic dimension (e.g., concreteness/abstractness or figurative language) or ask the model to justify its choice, to probe whether chain-of-thought reasoning improves reliability. Shot variation is tested with zero- and few-shot settings. Finally, we examine whether providing contextual metadata enhances the model’s ability to select appropriate senses and distinguish literal from figurative or abstract usage.

Case studies

We address the research questions outlined above through a series of targeted case studies conducted on a newly compiled diachronic Latin corpus of approximately one million words. The corpus spans multiple textual genres from the 3rd century BCE to the 20th century CE, enabling the observation of semantic behaviour across extended time spans, registers, and domains. Our approach is illustrated through representative case studies on selected Latin lexemes, chosen to exemplify high degrees of polysemy, shifts along the concrete–abstract continuum, and productive metaphorical/metonymic extensions across

periods and genres. For instance, *fructus* illustrates metaphor-driven abstraction from concrete reference ('fruit') to more abstract meanings ('outcome'), while *verbum* poses challenges of sense granularity and register sensitivity due to its rich semantics and long diachronic span ('word', 'discourse', 'proverb', 'God the Son'). Further cases capture metonymic alternations (e.g., *tectum* 'roof, house'), verbs whose meanings range from literal motion to idiomatic or abstract uses (e.g., *abeo* 'go away, terminate'), and adjectives that develop from physical perception to epistemic or evaluative meanings (e.g., *obscurus* 'dark, shady, obscure').

Keywords: Latin semantics, diachronic lexical semantics, sense inventories, metaphorical extension

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Automatic detection of formulaic expressions in Ancient Greek scientific (technical) texts

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Formulaicity is a hallmark of scientific language and terminology. This is a tendency to which Ancient Greek scientific language is no exception. This especially holds true for Ancient Greek ‘deductive’ sciences such as mathematics [6][6], in which field formulaic expressions can range from lower level multi-word expressions such as the (elliptic) ἡ AB γραμμῆ ‘the line AB’, to formulaic expression such as ἔστω X ‘let there be (geometrical shape)’, and to high-level comparison structures such as ὡς . . . οὕτως ‘as . . . so . . .’. Previous research on formulaicity in Ancient Greek has focused on epic formulaic language, but also on Ancient Greek Multi-Word Expressions (MWEs) [2], as well as more specifically on formulaic expressions in Ancient Greek mathematical texts [4, pp. 127-167]. Still, this research was largely qualitative, or made use of rudimentary measures such as N-grams: In the case of Fendel, the annotation of formulaicity relied on N-gram based preselection followed by manual verification of candidates; Netz on the other hand does not use any quantitative or automated method for his selection of formulas.

This presentation seeks to leverage quantitative methods to automatically detect candidates of formulaic expressions in Ancient Greek mathematical texts using the GLAUx corpus (Keersmaekers, 2021; 20 million tokens). We automatically select candidate formulaic expressions, not based on their linear proximity to each other in the sentence (as with N-grams), but rather on the basis of their syntactic relations. This is made possible by the syntactic annotation present in the GLAUx corpus. We then compute the significance of those co-occurrences with different measures. This methodology builds on the preexisting work of Martens & Vandeghinste (2010)[3], Sangati & Van Cranenburg (2015)[5] and Fantoli & Korkiakangas (2025)[1].

In a second step, we enrich these syntactic co-occurrences with semantic roles, which are also annotated in the GLAUx corpus. This accounts for semantic variation of constructions: it allows differentiation of syntactically equivalent constructions based on differences in the semantic roles of their constituents; conversely, it also facilitates detection of semantically equivalent but syntactically different constructions, such as is the case with passivization.

Finally, we plan to introduce automated provisional classification of the formula candidates: categories such as support verbs or light verb constructions can be identified by preselecting specific lemmas. Since these distinctions are mostly semantic in nature, this provisional classification constitutes a semantic classification task.

In adopting this exploratory strategy of formula detection, we reduce redundancy in two ways: as in previous research, we preclude interference of non-syntactic co-occurrences; next, we expand on this by exploiting semantic annotation, which prevents confusion of constructions on that score. The statistical information as well as the provisional categorization of said constructions serve as jumping off points for manual annotation. As such, our methodology facilitates the annotation and semantic classification of formulaic Ancient Greek expressions. In future this data may be used to train a language model to do the annotation automatically.

Keywords: formulaicity, multi word expressions, ancient Greek scientific language, treebanks, semantic roles, corpus linguistics

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1.2 Session 2: Fine-tuning and Vectorization

A Comparative Study of Static and Dynamic Vector Representations for Semantic Search in a Corpus of Classical Latin Texts

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With the rapid development of modern natural language processing methods, the problem of information retrieval has gained renewed importance, particularly in the context of ancient and historical texts [2][3].

Large and heterogeneous textual collections require representations that enable meaningful semantic access beyond surface-level keyword matching, while remaining robust to linguistic variation and limited data availability. For pre-modern languages, these challenges are further compounded by domain specificity and the lack of annotated resources [4][5]. Although several open repositories of Latin texts exist, including Corpus Corporum, the Perseus Digital Library, and PHI Latin Texts, most of them provide primarily lexical search and lack support for semantic search, which limits their applicability. This research addresses these issues through a comparative study of text vectorization methods for semantic search in a corpus of Classical Latin texts, examining how different representation strategies balance retrieval quality and computational efficiency, and how they can support semantic annotation workflows in the study of the ancient world.

The study investigates three families of vector representations that are commonly used as building blocks for semantic annotation pipelines and vector-based knowledge access systems: (1) static, non-trainable representations (TF-IDF); (2) static, trainable word embeddings (FastText [4]); and (3) contextual, dynamic embeddings derived from a pre-trained transformer model (Latin BERT [1]). While contextual models are often assumed to be superior due to their ability to capture specific semantic and syntactic information, their effectiveness for specialized ancient-language corpora remains an open question, particularly in scenarios with limited data, limited computational resources, and strong domain specificity.

The experimental corpus consists of approximately 506,000 words of Classical Latin prose and verse by Caesar, Cicero, Seneca, Manilius, Varro, Phaedrus, and Celsus, sourced from open digital repositories. For semantic search, longer works were segmented into smaller fragments to improve granularity and relevance assessment. A standardized preprocessing pipeline was applied using the Classical Language Toolkit (CLTK), including tokenization, normalization, stopword removal, and lemmatization; for Latin BERT, preprocessing was deliberately minimized to preserve contextual information. Document and query embeddings were stored and queried using a vector database (ChromaDB), enabling a reproducible evaluation of end-to-end semantic retrieval.

Search quality was evaluated using MAP@5 on a set of ten synthetic Latin queries, generated and assessed with the assistance of modern LLMs. In addition to retrieval quality, the study explicitly measures computational cost, including database construction time and average query latency, reflecting realistic constraints faced by many digital humanities projects.

The results reveal a counterintuitive but practically significant pattern. Despite its conceptual simplicity, TF-IDF (MAP@5 = 0.732) outperformed both pre-trained FastText (MAP@5 = 0.594) and Latin BERT (MAP@5 = 0.490) in retrieval quality, while also offering notably faster indexing and query times than the transformer-based approach. The weakest performance was observed for Latin BERT, which suffered from distribution shift: its pre-training data includes a mixture of classical texts and modern Latin, leading to semantic representations that are poorly aligned with the stylistic and thematic characteristics of the target corpus. In contrast, when FastText was further fine-tuned on the target Latin texts, it achieved the highest retrieval quality overall (MAP@5 = 0.843), surpassing both TF-IDF and Latin BERT while retaining high computational efficiency.

These findings have direct implications for information retrieval and semantic annotation in ancient world studies. First, they demonstrate that lightweight, interpretable, and adaptable models can outperform more complex architectures when domain specificity is critical. Second, they highlight the importance of corpus-aligned learning: fine-tuned embeddings capture domain-relevant conceptual proximity that can later be made explicit through links to controlled vocabularies, ontologies, or knowledge graphs. Third, the results caution against the uncritical application of powerful pre-trained LLM-based models in digital classics, reinforcing the need for transparency, evaluation, and human-in-the-loop validation.

This work argues for a pragmatic hybrid approach: using efficient, domain-adapted embedding models as an intermediate semantic layer that supports search, exploration, and annotation, while remaining compatible with explicit semantic representations and expert curation. Future work will focus on expanding

the evaluation benchmark with expert-generated queries and relevance judgments, exploring tighter integration between vector-based search and symbolic semantic annotation, and assessing how fine-tuned embeddings can be aligned with existing resources for ancient texts. By grounding AI-driven methods in careful empirical evaluation, this study contributes to more sustainable, transparent, and reusable digital infrastructures for classical and ancient studies.

Keywords: semantic search, information retrieval, digital humanities, machine learning

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Automatically enriching the GLAUx corpus with semantic role annotation

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Semantic roles (also known as thematic roles), which indicate the relation that the various participants hold to the event expressed by the verb, are a fundamental concept in verbal semantics. In linguistics, they are crucial in explaining morphosyntactic marking. Enriching ancient language corpora with semantic role annotation would therefore greatly enhance research possibilities in linguistics, as well as other fields, as their marking may allow researchers to search more efficiently for semantic concepts being expressed in various formal ways.

The focus of this paper is on Ancient Greek, for which no large corpora annotated with semantic roles exist yet. In [3] I proposed a first system for Ancient Greek semantic role labeling (SRL), based on random forests trained with various formal and semantic features. Meanwhile, in [4] I discussed possible standards for manual annotation, settling on the *FrameNet* annotation framework [1]. Although training data and a machine learning system already exists, considerable challenges still remain to enable large-scale SRL of Ancient Greek. Manual semantic annotation is labor-intensive, and the *FrameNet* role set is too fine-grained to train a machine learning system on. While more coarse-grained standards than *FrameNet* exist (e.g. [6][8]), the few of them that are mapped to *FrameNet* are only mapped partly. Additionally, the SRL system proposed in [3] was developed before transformer models for Ancient Greek were available, which could plausibly improve results given that they have done so in various domains of Ancient Greek NLP.

The goal of this paper is therefore twofold: (1) investigating possibilities for mapping FrameNet to various other standards, and (2) training new automated models for Ancient Greek semantic role labeling. Each of these goals will be discussed below.

1) Mapping FrameNet to other standards

As discussed above, various more other standards exist that provide a smaller, more manageable role set to train an automatic system on than *FrameNet*. I will consider three standards, viz. *VerbNet*[6], developed for English, *LIRICS* [8], developed from a cross-linguistic perspective, and *COMREGLA*[2], developed for Ancient Greek. While for *VerbNet* some mapping with *FrameNet* already exist, it is incomplete. Therefore, I will investigate the possibility of finetuning sentence embeddings of the description of the role in both resources so that the correct *VerbNet* (or *LIRICS*, *COMREGLA*) role can be selected that corresponds to the *FrameNet* role in question. This is done by finetuning Microsoft’s *MPNet* model in a bi-encoder and cross-encoder architecture. The first results, however, reveal that such a method requires a large amount of training data before satisfactory fully-automated results can be obtained, and that a semi-automatic approach with manual input might therefore be more feasible.

On a parallel level, I explore the automatic mapping of *WordNet* senses (synsets) to *FrameNet* frames: since GLAUx is annotated for *WordNet* synsets, this allows us to automatically assign frames to verbs in GLAUx and convert automatically assigned general roles such as those of *FrameNet* to more verb-specific roles, resulting in *FrameNet* annotation on a very large scale. The method is similar, finetuning *MPNet* in a bi-encoder/cross-encoder set-up. The results are much more satisfactory, with F1-scores reaching 0.95.

2) Training models for Ancient Greek semantic role labeling

Next, I will train an automatic semantic role labeling based on a dataset obtained by converting the *FrameNet* roles to a more coarse-grained system (having about 25000 tokens annotated with a semantic role). I will compare the older system proposed in [3], based on random forests, to a transformer-based system. I will investigate various ways in which transformer models may be used to perform automatic SRL prediction (including by finetuning and in combination with other features described in [3]), and compare several transformer models (including [10][7][9]). These results will be used to fully annotate the GLAUx corpus ([5], 20M tokens) with semantic role annotation.

While the semantic role annotation was primarily developed with linguistic purposes in mind, in a final part I will discuss the potential that such large-scale role annotation brings for various other fields such as ancient history.

Keywords: semantic roles, ancient Greek, linguistic annotation, machine learning

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Metadata conditioning for premodern Greek language models: Text annotation to preserve authorial style and meter in ancient text reconstruction

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Metadata conditioning is a state-of-the-art method of annotating text data according to specific metadata features (such as source, topic, and genre) in order to improve language model (LM) performance. Metadata conditioning has recently shown promise in improving decoder-only LM performance on downstream tasks, including next-token prediction [7][13][10]. This builds on wider research demonstrating the value of context-enhanced learning for model training [19][4]. Metadata conditioning often focuses on descriptive data labels like source URLs and text topics. But metadata conditioning may be used to aid humanities-based LM research by annotating LM pretraining text with metadata such as authorship, dialect, or textual form (e.g. prose vs verse). We believe this application of metadata conditioning may

help resolve persistent problems in LM research for ancient-language text reconstruction, principally the homogenization of distinct authorial vocabulary and grammar and generation of metrically inaccurate verse.

LM applications for ancient-language text reconstruction, notably filling textual lacuna, is a recently burgeoning area of scholarship [2][17][1][8]. Ancient languages provide a unique challenge in text reconstruction for several reasons, most notably: 1) particularly limited, finite data; 2) a tendency towards statistically-determined outputs in token prediction (potentially at odds with the principle of *lectio difficilior*); and 3) the prevalence of metrical texts. Unfortunately, LM applications for ancient languages have not addressed the possible utility of metadata conditioning via text annotations in LM pretraining for text reconstruction, which has shown promise for modern language LM applications. In this paper, we investigate the efficacy of metadata conditioning during LM pretraining as a means to help guide predictions along an author-specific vocabulary, as well as metrically accurate text, during gap-filling inference.

Indeed, although poetry-focused LM research is scarce, what research does exist in that area focuses on prepended metadata as a means to guide LM poetic text generation [14][3][5][18]. This research exclusively investigates text generation via decoder-only models for modern languages however. Moreover, this research often implements syllable and line-level annotations. Our paper charts new area in applying more metadata annotation to encoder-only models for gap filling of metrically-constrained texts in premodern languages.

Premodern Greek provides a particularly relevant test case for examining metadata conditioning. Combining existing premodern Greek corpora yields a sizeable dataset (~70 million words) compiled from multiple dialects—e.g. Attic, Koine, Byzantine, etc.—spanning textual forms and genres. In past research, this has required either 1) training on a dialect-specific subset, drastically reducing the available training data, or 2) pretraining a general premodern Greek LM, then fine tuning that model to a specific author or textual form for increased accuracy in downstream tasks (For case studies and in-depth discussions weighing such applications in philological research, see [11][9]). This process, though yielding a few philologically interesting results, proves cumbersome, inefficient, and still may not overcome linguistic homogenization. Pretraining LMs using text annotated with metadata labels nullifies the need for fine tuning by allowing users to condition model predictions via annotation labels during inference. For this presentation, we investigate different approaches to metadata annotation as an alternative to author or form-conditioned fine tuning.

Rather than decoder models, we pretrain and fine-tune encoder-only models. We focus on the later given bidirectional models' particular advantage in gap-filling, as well as current research focusing on encoder-only models for classical languages [12][16][6][15]. We compare two categories of models: 1) models pretrained with metadata conditioning and 2) models pretrained without metadata conditioning but fine-tuned to specific authors (e.g. Psellos) or text forms (e.g. hexameter). For the former, we annotate text data samples according to authorial source (e.g. Psellos, Aristotle, etc.) as well as textual form (i.e. prose, hexameter, trimeter, etc.). For the latter, we conduct standard pretraining and fine tuning with non-annotated data. In regards to metadata conditioning, we explore multiple avenues of text annotation for model pretraining, namely author embeddings and prepended annotation tokens. We then compare the performance of models pretrained using these separate forms of text annotation versus standard fine-tuned models without annotated data on a masked token prediction task. To this end, we provide an empirical investigation of whether metadata annotation may help guide masked token predictions along author-specific vocabulary and metrical patterns.

Keywords: premodern Greek, language models, metadata conditioning, text reconstruction, text annotation, context-aware training, classical languages

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1.3 Session 3: Annotation Workflows

Modular Annotation Framework for Ancient Greek Pedagogy

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This paper describes *Didakta Grammar for Annotation*, a modular framework designed to map the semantic and syntactic functions of Ancient Greek morphology through text annotation built for pedagogical purposes. *Didakta* is distinguished by its modular structure and unique tagging system, which enable cross-linguistic annotation portability. Rather than following the linear sequence typical of traditional grammar textbooks, *Didakta* organizes content into independent entries grouped by grammatical category (e.g., case, tense, mood, voice), with each entry describing specific semantic and syntactic functions. Each entry receives a unique identifier: for example, the locative dative is tagged *DatLoc*, the partitive genitive *GenPart*, and the optative of wish *OptWish*. These tags form a universal reference framework that remains identical across all language versions. *Didakta* currently has 127 entries and is available in English, Persian, Kurdish, and Brazilian Portuguese.

The development of *Didakta* was primarily based on Smyth's *A Greek Grammar for Colleges* [11], which served as a starting point, though both its content and structure were substantially revised. In keeping with *Didakta*'s emphasis on translatability, cross-linguistic comparisons between English and Ancient Greek were removed as part of this adaptation. The resulting framework was further enriched by incorporating more recent scholarship, including the *Cambridge Grammar of Classical Greek* [2] and the innovative *Pedalion Grammar* [12].

Didakta's defining feature lies in its language-independent unique identifiers: textual annotations using *Didakta* in one language automatically become accessible to speakers of all other languages into which *Didakta* has been translated. This cross-linguistic portability is achieved through the stable identifier assigned to each entry, which remains constant across translations. At the same time, the explanations linked to these tags are available in each learner's native language. This feature is particularly valuable for serving low-resource languages such as Kurdish or Persian. A single annotated text can serve learners across multiple languages without additional translation or conversion [7].

Initially implemented to address the challenge of teaching noun declension to Persian-speaking learners unfamiliar with grammatical cases, *Didakta* began as a pedagogical resource for explaining the syntactic and semantic roles of Ancient Greek cases in Persian. Its development was driven primarily by classroom experience of using treebanks to teach Ancient Greek, where the need for more detailed semantic explanations became apparent. The primary goal was to add a layer of interpretation to treebanks in order to support learners' understanding of the semantic roles of morphosyntactic forms. As a result, *Didakta*'s categories emerged as a complementary, more granular extension of existing treebanks, particularly Universal Dependencies, aiming to make implicit semantic distinctions explicit for pedagogical purposes.

The framework offers detailed categorizations of case usage, for instance, analyzing the genitive case through seventeen distinct entries. This granular approach proved beneficial for students whose native languages lack case systems. Recognizing that case analysis alone could not address the full spectrum of challenges in Ancient Greek pedagogy, *Didakta* then evolved to encompass verbal morphology, including entries for tense, mood, and voice [6]. These expansions extended *Didakta* into a comprehensive grammatical framework capable of annotating major morphosyntactic features of the Ancient Greek language.

Each entry in *Didakta* follows a consistent internal structure. Entries begin with the unique identifier tag that anchors the grammatical entry within the universal framework and enables cross-linguistic annotation. A detailed explanation then presents the semantic and syntactic role of the construction, followed

by examples from authentic Ancient Greek texts that illustrate each usage with citations linking directly to passages in the Perseus Digital Library and accompanied by English translations, as displayed in Figure 1 [10]. Finally, each entry provides references to parallel paragraphs in other sources, including the *Pedalion Grammar*, the *Cambridge Grammar of Classical Greek*, and Smyth's *Greek Grammar for Colleges*. *Didakta* was developed according to FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) to optimize its reuse and is available as open data on GitHub [5]. Originally developed in English and translated into Persian [8][9], it was later translated into Kurdish [4] and Brazilian Portuguese [3]. All four versions are distributed under an open license to ensure accessibility and enable further community-driven developments.

Didakta has been successfully deployed in two principal contexts: classroom instruction and text annotation. In classroom settings, *Didakta* has been used to teach Ancient Greek in Iran, the United States, and Brazil. For annotation purposes, it has been applied to Homer's *Iliad* Book One and *Odyssey* Book Five, where each morphological form is tagged with its corresponding *Didakta* identifier, linking text to grammatical explanations. The cross-linguistic nature of these annotations is particularly evident here: While *Odyssey* Book Five was annotated with *Didakta* tags by an English speaker, the annotations were later used in a course for Persian speakers who were able to access identical underlying annotations in their own language.

In addition to its role as a standalone resource, the *Didakta* grammar has also been featured as an interactive annotation resource within a next-generation digital library environment. In the *Beyond Translation* reading interface of the *Perseus Digital Library*, grammatical annotations drawn from the *Didakta* Modular Grammar appear alongside the Greek text of the *Iliad*. In this environment, words in the text that have corresponding entries in *Didakta* are highlighted, and clicking on a word displays the relevant *Didakta* entry or entries in a sidebar, allowing readers to engage with *Didakta* as an in-context grammatical commentary as they work through the passage [1].

While manual annotation using *Didakta* has demonstrated significant pedagogical value, the process remains labor-intensive and resource-demanding. Given that *Didakta* was developed as an additional, more granular layer on top of treebank annotations, its categories often exceed the level of detail represented in frameworks such as Universal Dependencies. As a result, existing treebank data can only support the automatic annotation of a limited subset of *Didakta* entries, particularly those corresponding to broad syntactic roles, such as nominative subjects or accusative objects. Finer semantic distinctions (e.g., locative dative) remain largely beyond the scope of automatic extraction. Consequently, annotation continues to rely primarily on manual input. Although the growing body of annotated texts may in the future support supervised machine learning approaches for token-level classification, mapping morphosyntactic features and contextual cues to *Didakta*'s fine-grained categories, the current manually annotated datasets remain too limited to enable reliable automation. Nonetheless, as a shared resource across multiple linguistic communities, *Didakta* has the potential to evolve into a large-scale, multilingual dataset that can significantly advance automated annotation.

Figure 1: Overview of the entry for the subjective genitive in *Didakta* Grammar for Annotation.

Keywords: digital classics, ancient Greek language pedagogy, open educational resources, multilingual annotations, low-resource languages

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Semi-Automated Semantic Annotation of Buddhist Murals: Integrating Foundation Models into a Digital Humanities Workflow

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Buddhist cave complexes in the region of Kucha, located along the northern Silk Road in present-day Xinjiang, house extensive mural paintings dating approximately from the fifth to the tenth centuries. Since their discovery in the early twentieth century, fragments of these paintings have been dispersed across museums worldwide, while the original caves have continued to deteriorate. (for further information see: [9][4][1][10]). Reconstructing the visual and historical context of these works therefore requires the integration of heterogeneous sources, including historical photographs, drawings, and surviving fragments.

The Kucha Murals Information System¹ addresses this challenge by documenting murals in situ and digitally re-integrating dispersed fragments into their original architectural and iconographic context [7]. A central methodological component is the systematic semantic annotation of visual material. Using the image annotation tool Annotorious², pictorial elements such as figures, attributes, gestures, and ornamental motifs are annotated directly in high-resolution images and linked to Kucha Murals Thesaurus³ comprising approximately 1,300 iconographic entries. These annotations enable precise scholarly referencing, support iconographic analysis across sites and collections, and provide structured data suitable for further computational processing, including knowledge graph construction and cross-modal research.

However, the creation of such annotations remains extremely labor-intensive and the scale of the annotation corpus has made it increasingly clear that purely manual workflows are not sustainable in the long term. The system currently contains more than 15,500 polygon annotations. This quantitative dimension requires not only efficiency improvements but also methodological rethinking.

Earlier attempts to address this challenge in the Project relied on region-based convolutional neural networks (R-CNNs) trained on previously annotated material.⁴ While these experiments demonstrated that object detection models can support annotation tasks under certain conditions, satisfactory results were largely limited to categories with a high number of training examples. Performance dropped significantly for less frequent iconographic elements, which are nevertheless often of high scholarly relevance. Moreover, segmentation quality frequently did not meet the geometric precision required for detailed art-historical analysis [6][5].

However, developments in recent years have opened up new possibilities. The emergence of so-called foundation models in the field of image processing has fundamentally widened the capabilities of tools and methods available for visual analysis. Foundation models are large neural networks trained on massive datasets using semi-supervised or self-supervised learning methods. Once trained, they can be adapted to a broad range of tasks without the need for task-specific retraining.

Although foundation models in image processing have not yet reached the versatility or performance levels of their language counterparts, recent advances show great promise. One particularly notable

¹www.kucha.saw-leipzig.de.

²www.annotorious.dev.

³www.kucha.saw-leipzig.de/kmt.

⁴R-CNNs (Region-Based Convolutional Networks) were first introduced by Girshick et al. in 2016 as a framework for object detection and segmentation combining region proposals with convolutional feature learning (Girshick et al. 2016).

development is Meta AI's Segment Anything Model (SAM) [2][8].

Segment Anything⁵ is a neural network trained on one of the largest segmentation datasets ever created, comprising over 1 billion masks across 11 million images. Unlike traditional segmentation models, SAM is promptable – it can be applied to new image distributions and tasks without additional training. This makes it a powerful tool for a wide range of uses.

This prompt-based interaction model significantly reconfigures the annotation workflow. Rather than replacing expert knowledge, it augments it: the scholar defines the object of interest, while the model generates a geometrically precise proposal that remains fully editable and verifiable. In this human-in-the-loop configuration, automation serves as an accelerant rather than an epistemic authority.

To operationalise this approach within the existing infrastructure, a custom extension was developed that integrates SAM directly into the Annotorious-based environment.⁶ The extension communicates with a dedicated server hosting the segmentation model, transmits prompt data, retrieves the generated masks, and converts them automatically into polygon annotations. This ensures seamless integration into the established taxonomy-driven annotation framework and preserves data consistency across the corpus.

Beyond improving efficiency, semi-automatic segmentation also contributes to methodological transparency and reproducibility. Because segmentation results are generated interactively and remain subject to expert verification, the process can be understood as a human-in-the-loop workflow rather than a fully automated pipeline. This aligns with current discussions in Digital Humanities that emphasise the integration of machine learning into controlled, interpretable workflows rather than fully automated pipelines[3].

Figure 1: Example of SAM embedded in the annotation process. the green region was selected with only one point.

Despite these advantages, the practical use of SAM also reveals limitations that are closely related to the way the model was trained. The training data underlying SAM consists of an extremely large number of comparatively small and highly localized segmentation masks [2]. As a consequence, the model performs particularly well when identifying clearly bounded individual objects. However, it shows significantly weaker performance when dealing with composite or structurally complex objects, such as clusters of buildings or larger architectural ensembles. In such cases, the model tends to segment individual components rather than the larger semantic unit intended by the annotator.

This behaviour is not merely a technical shortcoming but reflects a structural bias in the training data, in which little emphasis was placed on large, semantically coherent regions. Effective use of SAM in a scholarly annotation workflow therefore requires an awareness of these constraints and an adaptation of annotation strategies accordingly. Annotators must decide carefully at which semantic level segmentation should occur and, in some cases, combine or manually refine multiple masks to achieve the desired result.

⁵<https://ai.meta.com/research/sam2/>.

⁶<https://github.com/erikradisch/annotorious-selector-pack>; https://github.com/erikradisch/sam2_annotorious_server.

Furthermore, the resulting segmentations are not always geometrically stable. Masks may contain small holes, irregular boundaries, or “fuzzy” contours in areas where the network appears uncertain. Empirically, it can also be observed that adding further prompt points does not necessarily improve the result; in some cases, additional prompts appear to increase ambiguity rather than reduce it. For this reason, segmentation results must be critically evaluated and, where necessary, corrected before being incorporated into the scholarly dataset.

Figure 2: Prompt-induced instability in SAM segmentation: While a small number of corrective points can successfully close minor gaps (second image), additional prompts may increase mask fragmentation and “fuzzy” artefacts (third image), requiring substantially more intervention to restore a stable segmentation (fourth and fifth images)

The proposed paper will present the technical architecture of the system, discuss the impact of semi-automatic segmentation on annotation efficiency and quality, and discuss the implications of foundation models for visual scholarship in the Digital Humanities. By situating these developments within the broader context of semantic annotation and knowledge modelling, the paper aims to contribute to ongoing discussions about how hybrid AI approaches can support, rather than replace, expert interpretation in the study of cultural heritage.

Keywords: semi-automated image annotation, distant viewing, image annotation

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1.4 Session 4: Annotating Material Culture

Project RelNet: annotating temples, rituals and networks in Late Babylonia

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RelNet aims to explore Late Babylonian temple festivals on the basis of a set of 150 first-millennium BCE cuneiform tablets (mostly ritual texts) from institutional and private archives currently preserved in museum collections in Europe and the Middle East.

Text-bearing objects like cuneiform tablets provide multifaceted evidence that facilitates network analysis and helps to elucidate geographical relations across a wide range of case studies. On the one hand, one can scrutinise the relations between tablets, building networks using their metadata. On the other hand, one can create networks extracted from the contents of the documents themselves, to analyse their historical information as well as the social and spatial relations between the actors and places referred to in the texts. Previous projects have shown the potential value of cuneiform texts for the exploration of social networks [9][8][2][6][7]. Similarly, studies focusing on other regions and periods of the ancient world have demonstrated that the analysis of religiously motivated movements is crucial to elucidate the social function of rituals and sacred places [5][3][1][4].

The objective of RelNet is to shed new light on the study of sacred landscapes, cult topography and religious connections through network and geographical analysis using (a) Nodegoat⁷ as a platform for research data management and geographical and social network visualisations; (b) Recogito Studio⁸ for semantic annotation and data enrichment; and (c) Performant Studio⁹ as a front end to create an interactive, map-centred research platform to explore temples, travellers, texts and their geographic relationships.

As a first step, the network software environment Nodegoat is the perfect tool for modelling, visualising and analysing the kind of heterogeneous data we find in the texts. We can trace persons, places, events and relationships; store metadata alongside facsimiles, photos or copies; and link passages to people, places or concepts. In addition, we can map travel routes and other patterns.

Second, to capture spatial information within the narratives of ritual texts, we use Recogito Studio, an open-source tool from Pelagios, to identify the spatial elements mentioned in the texts (places, cities, temples...), and link these references to a global authority record. This authority record is provided by the Pleiades gazetteer, which assigns unique stable identifiers (URIs) to places in the ancient world. In this way we can map places referred to in the texts in a more exact and extensive way. We also use Recogito Studio's tagging function to provide additional information about each place or object.

Finally, the project will leverage Performant Studio, a package of open-source tools for digital humanities projects, which includes FairData and Core Data Places (a web framework with built-in mapping, search and browsing capabilities). The website will incorporate design elements from the existing University of Barcelona's RelNet website¹⁰ to maintain visual continuity with the project's established identity.

RelNet will combine all these approaches and tools to elucidate the spatial relations and the social and political function of temple festivals, as it will:

⁷<https://nodegoat.net/>

⁸<https://recogito-pelagios.netlify.app/en/sign-in>

⁹<https://www.performantsoftware.com/studio/>

¹⁰<https://www.ub.edu/relnet/>

(i) incorporate geospatial information (using, correcting and adding content to the Pleiades gazetteer) of intra- and inter-urban worship in Babylonia in order to identify itineraries and patterns in religious celebrations and examine the connections between cult centres; (ii) identify the actors, both divine and human, involved in the ceremonies; and (iii) investigate the deployment of the official religion in Babylonian society.

While cuneiform tablets containing temple ritual texts offer infinite possibilities for analysis, they also present a series of challenges related to both the nature of the sources and the methodology needed to explore them, which can affect the technical implementation of the project. In this paper I would like to highlight some of the most frequent issues encountered in relation to the nature of the sources (cuneiform texts with little archaeological or chronological context), and to underscore problems related to the methodology, such as the use of semantic annotation for Akkadian sources or the position of unknown or unlocated toponyms.

Keywords: cuneiform texts, Babylonian religion, temple festivals, sacred landscapes, cult topography, network analysis

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A Bridge between Text and Image: Multimodal AI and Ancient Greek Cultural Objects

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This paper emerges from doctoral research on the use of generative AI in the teaching of Ancient Greek. One of the central questions is whether AI-generated images can serve as a didactic tool to support the comprehension of ancient texts and stimulate semantic reflection among learners. What began as a practical pedagogical inquiry, however, opened onto a broader epistemological question: what does

it mean to “know” an ancient cultural object when its visualization is mediated by a system trained predominantly on modern representations of the past?

The rapid development of Multimodal Large Language Models (MLLMs) — also called Large Multimodal Models (LMMs) — has made the generation of images from textual prompts increasingly accessible and widespread, including in the domain of ancient texts. While these systems can produce visually fluent and compelling outputs, their application to the ancient world raises specific methodological and epistemological challenges. Images generated from ancient language texts are strongly conditioned not only by the limitations of the linguistic training data and by modern cultural representations of these periods (especially online images and video), but also by potential misunderstandings arising from semantic-conceptual overlaps between ancient Greek terms and their modern counterparts, semantic shifts and stratifications across time, and in some cases the absence of concrete object referents in the training material itself. When such texts are used as prompts for image generation — whether in the original language or in modern translation — the resulting images may differ significantly, not only in style but in their underlying conceptual interpretation.

This paper argues that these divergences reveal a deeper issue: the absence of an explicit semantic mediation layer between text and image, and proposes semantic annotation — a human-guided, interpretative practice — as a crucial bridge between ancient textual sources and multimodal AI systems.

The discussion is grounded in a case study drawn from the “True History” (“*Verae Historiae*”) by Lucian of Samosata, a text particularly suited to this investigation due to its rich descriptive passages and its play with visual imagination. A specific episode describing a bronze στήλη bearing a Greek inscription and marking the mythical passage of Heracles and Dionysus serves as the focal point of the analysis. The same passage was used as input for image generation with different ChatGPT models in two distinct forms: first, in the original Ancient Greek; second, in modern translation (Italian and English). The resulting images display systematic differences between the image generated by the original Greek text and those generated by translated text. These discrepancies are not random, nor are they easily attributable to stylistic variation. Instead, they reflect different implicit assumptions about the nature of the object being described — assumptions shaped by the convergence of linguistic, cultural, and training-data factors discussed above. The case of στήλη is particularly instructive in this regard: archaeological evidence provides a concrete and measurable point of comparison, allowing the gap between generated image and historical reality to be evaluated against what we already know the object to look like.

Crucially, however, the aim of this paper is not to obtain historically verisimilar reconstructions. Rather, the generative process — including its failures and distortions — is treated as an analytical and didactic instrument: a means of making visible the semantic assumptions that underlie both machine-generated imagery and human interpretation. When an AI system “visualizes” στήλη as an architectural column rather than a freestanding inscribed monument, this is not merely a technical error — it is an invitation to ask what it means to “know” an ancient cultural object, and whether working alongside generative AI might deepen, challenge, or productively unsettle that knowledge, both for researchers and for students of the ancient world.

Building on this, the paper introduces semantic annotation not as a technical preprocessing step, but as an analytical and interpretative layer. The Greek term στήλη does not simply denote a “column” in the architectural sense; it refers to a vertical monument — often inscribed — with commemorative, votive, or boundary-marking functions, and crucially, it is not a structural element of a building. Modern translations that render στήλη as “column” or “pillar” introduce a semantic shift that remains invisible unless it is made explicit through annotation.

By introducing a minimal semantic annotation — grounded in the philological analysis of the Greek term and formulated in English to optimize interpretability for the model — the analysis demonstrates how such clarification directly affects the outputs of multimodal AI systems. For instance, στήλη is annotated as “freestanding inscribed monument with commemorative or liminal function, non-architectural”,

a definition constructed ad hoc by a domain expert rather than drawn from a pre-existing ontology. This choice is methodologically deliberate: rather than delegating semantic mediation to standardized controlled vocabularies — which are predominantly written in English and structured around modern conceptual categories — the annotation is built case by case, starting from the Greek term in its specific textual and cultural context. In this way, the potential semantic slippage introduced using a modern language is not concealed but made explicit and analytically productive, consistent with the human-in-the-loop perspective that underlies the paper’s methodology. This collaborative framework allows for transparency and reflexivity: rather than treating generated images as self-evident representations of the text, they become objects of analysis that reveal how semantic ambiguities propagate across modalities.

The comparison between Greek and translated prompts also highlights the importance of semantic annotation in cross-lingual contexts. Translation inevitably involves interpretative decisions that may flatten or reframe culturally specific concepts. When such translations are used as inputs for multimodal generation, these decisions are amplified, producing images that may appear plausible but rest on anachronistic or culturally generic assumptions. Semantic annotation offers a way to reintroduce conceptual specificity, making visible what is gained, lost, or transformed in the transition from ancient language to modern representation — and in doing so, raises broader questions about how AI systems imagine the ancient world, and what this reveals about the relationship between human interpretation and machine-generated imagery.

These reflections carry direct implications for the teaching of Ancient Greek: interrogating how an AI visualizes *στῆλη* is not merely a technical exercise, but an invitation to engage with language, material culture, and historical imagination in ways that foster deeper cultural and anthropological understanding of the ancient world.

Keywords: AI, chatbot, ChatGPT, ancient Greek, semantic annotation, teaching ancient languages

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Evidence-Graded Semantic Annotation and Spatial Graph-RAG for Water Infrastructure in the Nile Valley (500 BCE–300 CE)

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Large language models can generate fluent environmental histories of the ancient Mediterranean on demand. Fluency, however, is precisely the danger: without an explicit semantic scaffold, LLM outputs tend to collapse heterogeneous evidentiary layers—attested statements, inferred events, and interpretive framings—into a single register of “facts.” For ancient environmental history, where genres moralize scarcity, narrate disaster through conventional tropes, or encode administrative action in documentary formulae, this collapse is methodologically corrosive. This paper argues that, if hybrid AI is to become genuinely useful for ancient-world research, semantic annotation must encode how claims function as evidence, and it must do so in a form that is both spatially actionable and computationally auditable.

We present a spatially-aware framework for studying water infrastructure in the ancient Mediterranean across heterogeneous textual corpora. The framework parses open, machine-actionable texts (TEI and EpiDoc XML), links places to a gazetteer-based spatial authority layer (Pleiades identifiers enriched with environmental data), and stores the result in an auditable Neo4j knowledge graph that enables provenance-aware querying and inspection of how answers are produced. On top of this substrate, the system supports graph-augmented retrieval-augmented generation (Spatial Graph-RAG) for citation-based question answering, where retrieval is not only semantic (vector-based) but also constrained by explicit scholarly criteria (place, region, period, source type, and evidence status). The paper’s contributions are: (1) an evidence-graded semantic annotation model tailored to environmental and infrastructural claims, (2) a practical integration of that model with spatial authority data, environmental signatures, and an auditable graph design across both literary and documentary corpora, and (3) a retrieval strategy that uses semantic annotation as the mechanism of transparency and scholarly control in hybrid AI workflows.

A methodological hinge of the approach is a versioned controlled vocabulary (the “Ancient Ecology Vocabulary,” currently v0.3 with 80 terms), designed to function simultaneously as the label set for NLP extraction and as a reusable semantic layer for cross-project interoperability. The vocabulary is grounded in Bonneau’s (1993) administrative terminology for Nile water management and extended

to cover the broader Mediterranean, targeting ecological and infrastructural knowledge at a granularity appropriate for historical interpretation: hydraulic features (canals, dikes, basins, nilometers, wells, cisterns, harbors), hydrological phenomena (inundation regimes, low-water years, flood anomalies, siltation), management practices (irrigation, dredging, embankment repair, canal clearance, water-lifting and distribution), and interpretive framings commonly encountered in ancient sources (divine agency, mismanagement, natural cycles, moral exemplum). The vocabulary is applied during text processing, producing annotations that can be queried structurally rather than by keyword alone. Cross-corpus analysis validates the design: documentary papyri show a 10.6% vocabulary annotation rate versus 1.9% for literary texts, confirming that the vocabulary captures the administrative and infrastructural register of documentary sources far more densely than literary prose.

The key technical move is an evidence-graded annotation model, following the HiCo ontology Daquino & Tomasi (2015), that classifies every passage according to how it functions as evidence. Each passage receives one of three evidence-layer labels. Attestation marks passages that constitute direct evidence of a practice, event, or state of affairs—typically administrative documents, contracts, receipts, and inspection records where the text is itself a trace of the activity it describes. Inference marks passages where an author reports or generalizes about practices and conditions without being a direct witness or participant—for instance, a literary geographer describing how irrigation works in a region he surveys. Framing marks passages where the dominant register is rhetorical or explanatory rather than descriptive—prodigy narratives, moral diagnoses of environmental crisis, divine-punishment accounts of drought or flood. These labels are assigned during an LLM-assisted classification, and the distribution validates the model: documentary papyri are classified as 99.8% attestation, while literary texts show a more varied distribution (64% attestation, 34% inference, 2% framing), reflecting the fundamental generic difference between administrative records and literary prose. This classification enables queries that no keyword search can support: a scholar can ask for all direct administrative evidence of canal maintenance in the Arsinoite nome, excluding literary descriptions and moralizing framings, and the system returns only the documentary attestations.

Methodologically, the workflow combines supervised NLP models with LLM-assisted classification. Named entity recognition extracts place names, person names, and organizations from text. In parallel, an LLM-assisted annotation stage performs constrained classification against the controlled vocabulary, producing links from passages to vocabulary concept identifiers along with confidence scores and classification rationales. For documentary papyri, a second entity source supplements NER: structured metadata from the Heidelberger Gesamtverzeichnis provides provenance locations with Trismegistos GEO identifiers, date ranges, and document-type keywords. All toponyms—whether extracted by NER or provided by metadata—are reconciled to Pleiades identifiers via a concordance built from the Pleiades gazetteer, and promoted to first-class graph nodes organized into 44 ancient administrative regions. The resulting graph is deliberately designed so that text segments, places, regions, environmental data, and infrastructure concepts are mutually indexable: it is a queryable evidentiary substrate rather than a narrative output.

On top of this substrate, Spatial Graph-RAG couples vector retrieval with graph constraints. Natural-language queries are first analyzed for structured hints—place names are matched to regions, temporal references to date ranges, domain terms to vocabulary concepts—and these hints generate graph constraints that filter candidate passages by place, region, period, source type, infrastructure category, and evidence layer (attestation vs. inference vs. framing). Semantic search then ranks within the filtered set. The LLM is therefore not the sovereign narrator but a synthesis layer operating over an explicitly modeled, provenance-aware graph: answers are returned with citable passages and retrieval metadata, and the system can present attestations separately from inferred reconstructions and rhetorical framings. This design directly targets a central problem in applying LLMs to ancient evidence—hallucination and evidentiary flattening—by making citation, provenance, and epistemic status first-class constraints rather than post-hoc expectations.

We motivate the approach through a Nile Valley case study (500 BCE–300 CE), selected because it is both rich and difficult: it forces the system to negotiate genre diversity, uneven preservation, and shifting administrative and rhetorical registers, while supporting the questions historians actually ask about water as practice, risk, and governance capacity. The evaluation addresses two dimensions. For annotation quality, we assess consistency of evidence-layer assignment (attestation/inference/framing) and controlled-vocabulary labeling against existing gold-standard annotations from established digital humanities projects. For retrieval and answering, we test whether graph-constrained retrieval improves spatial and temporal specificity compared to unconstrained semantic retrieval, using task-oriented queries across 171 expert questions and 283 automatically generated questions. The resulting methodology is intended to be reusable beyond the Nile Valley: it treats semantic annotation as an interpretive contract that makes hybrid AI accountable to ancient evidence, and it provides a practical path from annotated texts to auditable, spatially grounded scholarly querying.

Keywords: semantic annotation, evidence-graded annotation, knowledge graphs, provenance, spatial annotation, Pleiades, TEI/EpiDoc, controlled vocabularies, Graph-RAG, RAG, Nile Valley water infrastructure

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1.5 Session 5: Human-in-the-loop Annotation

Rethinking Genre Classification and the Digitally-Annotated Great Unread: The Case of Talmudic Stories

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The term ‘genre classification’ carries within it an inherent tension, suggesting that determining a text’s genre is synonymous with classifying it. From a theoretical standpoint, however, this is a controversial assumption, as genres are fundamentally more “types” than “classes”: they are fluid structures that may materialize in a single instance or, at times, not at all; they are intended to provide an essential interpretive key to each of their realizations, rather than just a way to organize them together; and, as some scholars suggest, the relationship between them and their measured textual evidences is akin to that between icebergs and their visible tops. While the digital age increasingly forces us to categorize literature by grouping instances together based on these icebergs’ tops, their distinctive quality as types remains somewhat hidden. This proposal seeks to explore the intersection of literary genre theory and computational practice, using the semantic annotation of Talmudic stories as a test case for rethinking how we map the “one” and the “many” in the digital sphere.

The study of the Babylonian and Yerushalmi Talmuds - foundational legal-interpretive works totaling 2.7 million words - has long been dominated by a tiny “scholarly canon” of only a few hundred stories. This narrow focus leaves the “great unread” - approximately 10,000 narrative units in Hebrew and Aramaic - largely unexplored. To challenge this limited image, our eight-year project involves collecting the entire corpus into a database; enriching it with multi-layered literary annotations (historical, linguistic, and narratological); and analyzing the results through distant reading, harnessing text analysis techniques - suitably adapted to the source languages of the material - alongside tag-based analysis. Mapping these unseen reaches raises fundamental questions, as the limited scholarly canon produced a genre map that proved ineffective for the complete corpus; and as computational workflows often require categorical grouping, forcing a shift from flexible ‘types’ to rigid ‘classes’ based on measurable markers rather than more essential literary aspects.

This challenge is particularly acute in the study of ancient texts whose underlying genre logic is not always accessible to us, and where automated classification risks ‘flattening’ meaning. For instance, pre-LLM models often prioritize style over plot depth, creating an abundance of micro-genres rather than providing an interpretive key. While LLM-based methods have been tested in our lab, initial results in capturing the nuances of Talmudic genres highlight the continued need for human-in-the-loop grounding to ensure semantic precision.

Our semantic mapping has already led to some critical discoveries. Expanding the corpus revealed several previously unrecognized or hybrid genres and encouraged a rethink of the overall structure of the genre map. For example, we found that the traditional canon was primarily defined by a specific

story length (80–160 words); by investigating stories whose length falls outside this canonical range - both significantly shorter and longer - we identified new genres and gained a better understanding of the relationship between creativity and formulaic narrative components.

Based on these findings, we developed database guidelines that balance manual expertise with computational power. Rather than forced grouping, we identify the unique qualities of individual stories through expert tagging that includes clearly measurable elements alongside more complex, interpretation-based poetic features. Our approach supports hybrid and multi-layered classification, allowing one story to fall into multiple categories and enabling both tabular and network analysis; these meaning-driven ontologies combine traditional identifications with a new genre map where feature combinations carry meaning as a "type" rather than a mere "class."

In this lecture, I will offer a reflection on the conceptual journey of our project; I will demonstrate how we move beyond a reliance on rigid "classes" by constantly striving to identify the underlying "types" that govern the narrative. In the end, genre remains the "flash point" where the individual and the group meet; by utilizing semantic annotation to rethink "the one and the many," we can move beyond the traditional canon to map the "great unread" without sacrificing depth for technical convenience.

Keywords: genre classification, distant reading, categorization, genre theory, Talmud, narratology

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Coding Narrative Dynamics in Plutarch's Metaphors

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When annotating Plutarch's metaphors, the research team working on the "Thinking of Thinking..." project (NCN Sonata Bis, no. 2021/42/E/HS3/00259; PI: Julia Doroszewska) has encountered important methodological and procedural challenges. Metaphor types such as direct, mixed, and underspecified are usually coded with little disagreement in the database; it is the cluster provisionally called "extended" or "narrative" that proves most difficult.

A good example is Gryllus 989C–D, which brings the annotation dilemmas into focus. Here Gryllus the Pig explains to Odysseus the difference between animal and human temperance by representing the soul as a polity. He argues:

But there is a tribe (γένος) of desires — desires neither necessary nor natural, but poured in from outside (ἔξωθεν . . . ἐπικεχυμένων), driven by empty opinions because of ignorance of beauty; by its sheer multitude it has all but effaced (ἀπέκρυσεν) almost all your native desires (φυσικάς), like a throng of foreign newcomers in a city overpowering its native citizenry. But beasts, having souls wholly inaccessible to foreign passions and unmixed with them (ἀβάτους καὶ ἀνεπιμίκτους ἔχοντα τοῖς ἐπεισάκτοις πάθει τὰς ψυχὰς), and in their way of life keeping themselves far (πόρρω . . . ἀπωκισμένα) from empty opinion as though from the sea, lack only delicate and luxurious living; rather, they carefully guard (διαφυλάττεται) their moderation and the good government (εὐνομεῖσθαι) of their desires, since those dwelling within them are neither numerous nor foreign (οὔτε πολλαῖς συνουκούσαις οὔτ' ἄλλοτρίαις).

The first issue concerns the level of detail at which the passage should be annotated. Collapsing it into one overarching conceptual metaphor (MIND IS A POLIS) flattens the argumentative dynamics of invasion and resistance, whereas splitting it into discrete X-is-Y pairs risks disarticulating what functions as an organic figurative whole.

The second issue concerns the identification of the elements that properly belong to the metaphor under discussion. Especially revealing here are the expressions of liquid imagery (“poured in” and “keeping far, as from the sea”), which might seem to introduce a second metaphorical pattern superimposed on the civic one. Yet the fact that Plutarch elsewhere uses liquid imagery for demographic pressure (cf. *Quaest. conv.* 729F; *De exilio* 602E) and foreign influx (*Pyrrh.* 33.5; *De genio Socr.* 598E) makes it preferable to treat this not as a parallel image that would render the passage a mixed metaphor, but as a secondary figurative layer embedded within the dominant scenario: FOREIGNERS ARE LIQUID, which transforms into DESIRES ARE FOREIGNERS.

A third issue arises from the wider textual context: since the mind-as-city imagery reappears later, at *Gryllus* 989F (“no foreign desires inhabit our minds”), how can one determine where the textual boundary of this elaborated metaphor properly lies? A related boundary problem concerns the distinction between the metaphor proper and its comparative framing, represented here by the two brief clauses cited above. Indeed, is the figure under discussion a metaphor at all, or does it incline rather toward simile or allegory? At the same time, this passage is sufficiently dynamic to bring into focus the main annotation problem that recurs in many borderline Plutarchan cases: by what criteria should the passage count as a narrative metaphor in the first place, especially where temporal progression and spatial development are compressed rather than explicit?

The problem of such metaphorical ensembles is as much terminological as technical: in current scholarship, the labels ‘extended’, ‘threaded’ and ‘narrative’ metaphor partly overlap, but on closer inspection, they do not designate the same structural and functional phenomenon [10][7][9][1]. This paper argues that extension and narrativity must be analytically separated if annotation is to remain both reproducible and interpretatively adequate. We test this claim on Plutarchan passages ranging from high-resolution cases (*Gryllus* 989C-D, *Adv. Col.* 1120C-D) to borderline formations (*De cur.* 518B, *De aud. poet.* 14F-15A.), as well as counterexamples where figurative accumulation fails to produce internal development (*De Alex. fort.* 339A, *Gryllus* 989F). While the distinction between extending and elaborating metaphor [4] is helpful here, it is insufficient. As the paper shows, this must be supplemented with a scenario-based account of figurative inference and the concept of generic templates [5][6][3].

Methodologically, we propose three sine qua non conditions for annotating a passage as a narrative metaphor: (i) it must contain several semantically interrelated lexical units that represent a single source–target mapping; (ii) these units must occupy distinct syntagmatic positions, either within one clause or across phrase-level units; and (iii) they must preserve sufficient semantic distance to generate differentiated entailments (e.g., eventive shift, directional motion, role replacement, or focal reorientation). This allows one to capture minimal narrativity even in compressed forms, such as eventfulness without significant expansion, motion without an explicit plot, role-based transformation without a finite event structure,

and micro-shifts within a single, coherent scenario. These minimal dynamics align with psycholinguistic accounts of situation-model updating [8] and with blending-based models of constructing fictitious scenarios from sparse linguistic stimuli [6]. At the same time, the model prevents over-reading: coordinated doublets or stylistic synonymia are not automatically treated as narrative elements unless internal development is activated [2][11].

The annotation workflow proposed in this study is human-in-the-loop and is designed to produce consistent, reusable, and machine-actionable records. This workflow proceeds through seven stages: delimitation; metaphoricity screening; source-domain coherence; syntagmatic distribution; tautology filtering; internal-dynamics testing; and boundary diagnostics against neighbouring figures (simile, allegory, and mixed metaphor). The resulting annotation records are therefore detailed enough for interpretive philology, yet remain methodologically consistent and reusable. Rather than seeking to automate metaphor interpretation, the paper establishes a reusable semantic layer that facilitates machine-assisted retrieval, consistency checks, and cross-corpus comparisons in ancient prose.

Keywords: ancient Greek prose, conceptual metaphor, cross-domain mapping, corpus analysis, extended metaphor, human-in-the-loop, metaphor annotation, narrative metaphor, Plutarch, semantic dynamics, scenario-based inference

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Coding the Uncodable? Manual Semantic Annotation of Cognition Metaphors in Plutarch Between Interpretive Labor and Hybrid AI Workflows

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Large language models (LLMs) can generate fluent interpretations of ancient texts, yet their outputs often remain difficult to audit: they rarely make explicit *which* textual evidence supports a claim and *how* competing readings were resolved. Semantic annotation promises a remedy by turning interpretation into

structured, inspectable, and reusable evidence. At the same time, metaphor studies expose a persistent methodological tension: the phenomena we care about are frequently context-dependent and concept-driven rather than keyword-driven, and therefore resist “automatic discovery” in the absence of carefully defined categories, guidelines, and human adjudication. This paper addresses that tension through a case study from the research project *Thinking of Thinking: Conceptual Metaphors of Cognition in the Plutarchan Corpus* (2022–2027), which investigates cognition metaphors across Plutarch’s *Lives* and *Moralia* and curates the results in the Plutarch Metaphor Observatory (PMO), an online database of record-level annotations with stable identifiers.¹¹

Following Conceptual Metaphor Theory, we treat metaphors as systematic mappings that structure a target domain (here, cognition) in terms of a more concrete source domain. In Plutarch, cognition is frequently construed via domains such as VISION (e.g., understanding framed as “seeing,” “making clear,” or “bringing to light”), MOTION/PATH (reasoning as moving forward, progressing, deviating, or being led), CONTAINMENT (ideas “in” the mind; memory as storing/holding), and MANUAL ACTION (comprehension as grasping/handling). Our focus is not on isolated “poetic” metaphors, but on recurring metaphor families that shape how cognitive states and processes are conceptualized in narrative, argument, and moral discourse.

The project’s methodological choice is consequential: our target domain is intentionally broad—*cognition* and cognitive processes/states (e.g., understanding, learning, remembering/forgetting, judging, deliberating, believing, and related mental activities). If the analytical target were a narrow lexical set, a traditional strategy—searching a digital corpus (e.g., TLG-style keyword search) for a small list of “mind-words”—could recover many passages with acceptable recall. By contrast, cognition metaphors in Ancient Greek are distributed across heterogeneous lexical items, constructions, and rhetorical frames, and they are often realized without explicit cognitive terminology. For this reason, the project was designed as manual-first: we aim to identify and classify *conceptual mappings*, not merely word occurrences. The resulting dataset is therefore best understood not as a list of “found” expressions, but as the record of systematic interpretive decisions that link textual spans to conceptual structures.

The paper presents the project’s manual annotation scheme as a response to this interpretive–technical tension and as a model for making philological judgement *accountable* rather than opaque. The scheme distinguishes three linked layers: (1) a text anchoring layer (work and passage identifiers plus an explicit span reference), (2) a linguistic layer (the attested Greek form(s), with lemmatization and relevant contextual notes), and (3) a conceptual layer that captures the mapping between a cognitive target (a sub-area of cognition) and a source domain, together with a metaphor-family label that supports aggregation and comparison (e.g., KNOWING-AS-SEEING; REASONING-AS-A-PATH). A central design commitment is standardization via controlled inventories of target categories and source domains, enabling aggregation without collapsing interpretive nuance.

Because manual semantic annotation at this scale has significant labor implications, we treat labor and credit as part of the research design rather than an invisible prerequisite. The corpus scope is substantial (covering the *Lives* and the *Moralia*), and the work is distributed across roles that include annotation, review, curation, and technical maintenance. Our release plan is staged: a calibrated, adjudicated benchmark subset is prepared for public release first, followed by periodic dataset updates as curation progresses. Each record is intended to remain citable at the instance level via stable identifiers and persistent record addresses, and releases will include contributor metadata (including role descriptions and, where available, ORCID), so that annotation and curation labor are explicitly creditable.

A major theme of the paper is the epistemic role of human annotators. In metaphor annotation, expertise is not limited to mechanical tagging; annotators determine (i) whether a passage is metaphorical or

¹¹The project is funded by the National Science Centre, Poland (agreement no. 2021/42/E/HS3/00259), and carried out at the Faculty of History, University of Warsaw, under the direction of Julia Doroszevska. The Plutarch Metaphor Observatory digital database (<https://corpus.plutarch.uw.edu.pl/>) has been created by Bartosz Maćkiewicz aided by Katarzyna Kuś. All the records were prepared by Julia Doroszevska, Angelina Gerus, Orestis Karatzoglou, and Laurens van der Wiel.

conventionalized, (ii) how to delimit the relevant span, (iii) how to choose among competing source domains, and (iv) how to specify the cognitive subtarget when multiple processes overlap (e.g., deliberation vs. evaluation). These decisions are shaped by philological context, genre expectations, and discourse function, not only by lexicon. We therefore treat annotation as an interpretive practice that must be transparent, reproducible, and reviewable.

To ensure that manual annotation does not collapse into idiosyncratic reading, the paper reports a sample-based quality-control procedure already implemented in the project: selected passages were double-annotated; a third team member reviewed agreements and disagreements and coordinated an adjudication discussion. This workflow serves two purposes. First, it improves internal consistency by calibrating annotators and refining guidelines. Second, it makes disagreement analytically productive: recurrent divergence points reveal where cognition metaphors are genuinely underdetermined by linguistic form alone (for instance, cases where one expression plausibly evokes competing source domains, or where the cognitive target is implicit rather than named). We summarize recurrent disagreement types (span delimitation, competing domain assignment, borderline metaphor status, implicit mappings) as an empirical map of difficulty that any automated approach would have to confront.

This leads to our core argument about the manual-automatic tension. We do not claim that automation is impossible. Rather, we argue that full automatic annotation is ill-posed at the outset when the target domain is broad, concept-driven, and rhetorically mediated; The task becomes tractable only after the project has created the conceptual infrastructure that automation requires: controlled inventories, adjudicated examples, documented edge cases, and repeatable quality-control procedures. In that sense, the dataset is not merely “ground truth for LLMs,” but a reusable, structured representation of expert interpretation. At the same time, we identify concrete components that are appropriate for partial automation now and, crucially, for reuse of existing resources rather than duplication of effort. On the linguistic layer, lemmatization and morphosyntactic information can be aligned with existing Ancient Greek treebank resources and infrastructures (e.g., AGLDT/Perseus treebanks, Gorman’s Ancient Greek prose dependency treebanks, and platforms such as GLAUx where coverage permits), reducing repeated work and improving comparability. On the conceptual layer, we discuss alignment opportunities with reference to lexico-semantic resources such as Ancient Greek WordNet as a background for normalizing and relating conceptual labels, even when metaphor families do not map one-to-one onto synset structure.

A further concern addressed here is generalizability. Because our corpus and task are highly specific (Plutarch; cognition metaphors), we do not present the dataset as a universal training resource for generic metaphor detection. Instead, we articulate realistic reuse scenarios: (i) domain-specific scholarly querying and comparison of cognition-metaphor patterns across works and genres; (ii) alignment experiments that connect metaphor annotations to external linguistic resources for Ancient Greek; (iii) evaluation of semi-automatic workflows (candidate retrieval, label suggestion from controlled inventories, consistency checking) where humans retain responsibility for final decisions; and (iv) methodological transfer of the quality control and adjudication model to other interpretive annotation tasks in the ancient world.

Finally, we specify the form of the project’s planned data release: a documented, versioned export in widely usable formats such as CSV and JSON, with clearly defined fields, stable identifiers, and machine-readable metadata, rather than ad hoc spreadsheets. The publicly available database already assigns stable record identifiers and supports record-level citation; future releases will extend this through persistent, resolvable record addresses for individual PMO entries. This supports FAIR-oriented practice and keeps the resource structurally ready for future Linked Open Data pathways without requiring immediate publication as a fully RDF-based edition.

In sum, this paper argues that semantic annotation in the ancient world is not simply a technique for making texts machine-readable; it is a way of making interpretation auditable and creditable. Where the target domain is conceptually expansive and rhetorically mediated, human annotation is not a bottleneck but the mechanism by which categories become stable, reusable, and transparent—and by which selective, well-scoped automation becomes meaningful rather than performative.

Keywords: manual semantic annotation, conceptual metaphor, ancient Greek, Plutarch, cognition, controlled vocabularies, quality control, human-in-the-loop, FAIR data, interoperability

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Keyword Index

- AI 29
- ancient Greek 16, 29, 39
- ancient Greek language pedagogy 22
- ancient Greek prose 36
- ancient Greek scientific language 13
- Babylonian religion 27
- categorization 34
- chatbot 29
- ChatGPT 29
- classical Arabic 8
- classical languages 18
- clause modeling 6
- cognition 39
- conceptual metaphor 36, 39
- context-aware training 18
- controlled vocabularies 32, 39
- corpus analysis 36
- corpus linguistics 13
- cross-domain mapping 36
- cult topography 27
- cuneiform texts 27
- diachronic lexical semantics 11
- digital classics 22
- digital humanities 15
- distant reading 34
- distant viewing 25
- early Arabic poetry 8
- evidence-graded annotation 32
- extended metaphor 36
- FAIR data 39
- formulaicity 13
- frame semantics 8
- genre classification 34
- genre theory 34
- Graph-RAG 32
- historical research 6
- human-in-the-loop 36, 39
- image annotation 25
- information retrieval 15
- interoperability 39
- knowledge graphs 32
- language models 18
- Latin semantics 11
- linguistic annotation 16
- low-resource languages 22
- machine learning 15, 16
- manual semantic annotation 39
- metadata conditioning 18
- metaphor annotation 36
- metaphorical extension 11
- multi word expressions 13
- multilingual annotations 22
- narrative metaphor 36
- narratology 34
- network analysis 27
- Nile Valley water infrastructure 32
- NL2Code 8
- ontology building 6
- open educational resources 22
- Pleiades 32
- Plutarch 36, 39
- premodern Greek 18
- provenance 32
- quadruple 6
- quality control 39
- RAG 32
- sacred landscapes 27
- scenario-based inference 36
- semantic annotation 6, 29, 32
- semantic dynamics 36
- semantic roles 13, 16
- semantic search 15
- semi-automated image annotation 25
- sense inventories 11
- spatial annotation 32
- Talmud 34
- teaching ancient languages 29
- TEI/EpiDoc 32
- temple festivals 27
- text annotation 18
- text reconstruction 18
- treebanks 13

Author Index

Da Riva, Rocio 26
Di Pasqua, Federico 30
Doroszewska, Julia 36

Fantoli, Margherita 12
Farina, Andrea 9

Gerus, Angelina 34
Graziosi, Barbara 17

Hampeš, Tomáš 6
Hanák, Petr 6

Karatzoglou, Orestis 36
Keersmaekers, Alek 12, 15
Kuś, Katarzyna 34

Lamar, Annie 5

Marienberg-Milikowsky, Itay 33
Maćkiewicz, Bartosz 36
McGillivray, Barbara 9
Merialdo, Paolo 30

Mertel, Adam 6
Murel, Jacob 17

Nurmikko-Fuller, Terhi 5

Pietrzak, Bartosz 6

Radisch, Erik 23

Semenov, Ivan 13
Shamsian, Farnoosh 20
Shaw, Robert L. J. 6

Tartaglia, Alessia 27
Torlone, Riccardo 30

Van Hal, Toon 12

Windelinckx, Martijn 12

Yuan, Sarah 17

Zbírál, David 6